

Investigation of alternative RF power limit control methods for 0.5T, 1.5T, and 3T parallel transmission cardiac imaging: A simulation study

Johannes Petzold^{1,2} |
Oliver Speck²

¹Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB), Braunschweig and Berlin, Germany

²Biomedical Magnetic Resonance, Otto von Guericke University Magdeburg, Magdeburg, Germany

Correspondence

Johannes Petzold,
Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt,
Abbestr. 2-12, 10587 Berlin, Germany.
Email: johannes.petzold@ptb.de

Funding information

European Metrology Programme for Innovation and Research, Grant/Award Number: 17IND01; European Partnership on Metrology, Grant/Award Number: 21NRM05

Abstract

Purpose: To investigate safety and performance aspects of parallel-transmit (pTx) RF control-modes for a body coil at $B_0 \leq 3T$.

Methods: Electromagnetic simulations of 11 human voxel models in cardiac imaging position were conducted for $B_0 = 0.5T, 1.5T$ and $3T$ and a body coil with a configurable number of transmit channels (1, 2, 4, 8, 16). Three safety modes were considered: the ‘SAR-controlled mode’ (SCM), where specific absorption rate (SAR) is limited directly, a ‘phase agnostic SAR-controlled mode’ (PASC), where phase information is neglected, and a ‘power-controlled mode’ (PCM), where the voltage amplitude for each channel is limited. For either mode, safety limits were established based on a set of ‘anchor’ simulations and then evaluated in ‘target’ simulations on previously unseen models. The comparison allowed to derive safety factors accounting for varying patient anatomies. All control modes were compared in terms of the B_1^+ amplitude and homogeneity they permit under their respective safety requirements.

Results: Large safety factors (approximately five) are needed if only one or two anchor models are investigated but they shrink with increasing number of anchors. The achievable B_1^+ is highest for SCM but this advantage is reduced when the safety factor is included. PCM appears to be more robust against variations of subjects. PASC performance is mostly in between SCM and PCM. Compared to standard circularly polarized (CP) excitation, pTx offers minor B_1^+ improvements if local SAR limits are always enforced.

Conclusion: pTx body coils can safely be used at $B_0 \leq 3T$. Uncertainties in patient anatomy must be accounted for, however, by simulating many models.

KEYWORDS

electromagnetic simulation, parallel transmission, patient model uncertainty, position uncertainty, RF safety, safety factor

This is an open access article under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

© 2023 Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB). *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine* published by Wiley Periodicals LLC on behalf of International Society for Magnetic Resonance in Medicine.

1 | INTRODUCTION

Parallel transmission (pTx)¹⁻⁴ is a powerful tool to deal with RF inhomogeneities and is frequently considered indispensable for ultrahigh field (UHF) body MRI with $B_0 \geq 7T$.⁵⁻⁹ At 'clinical' field strengths ($B_0 \leq 3T$), two-channel configurations are becoming increasingly available at 3T,¹⁰⁻¹⁶ while pTx with higher channel counts or for even lower field strengths exists only in a handful of research scanners.¹⁷⁻²⁵ Two reasons have been given to explain why pTx with channel counts >2 never really became a standard at $B_0 \leq 3T$. First, pTx is supposed to be costly. This argument has become less important, however, since today's RF power amplifiers (RFPA) are often based on a stack of ~ 1 -kW power MOSFETs,^{26,27} which could be fed separately for pTx instead of stacking them for a single channel transmission. Second, its benefit at $B_0 \leq 3T$ might not outweigh the additional effort to ensure patients' safety.¹⁶

Today, (static) pTx is used in modern 3T systems with two Tx channels for body imaging to address spatial heterogeneities of the flip angle and, thus, the signal and image contrast.¹⁶ Cardiac²⁵ and quantitative MR have been shown to benefit particularly from pTx with more than two channels because of improved B_1^+ homogeneity.^{18,28,29} Arguably even more important are pTx benefits for the safety of implant-carrying patients.³⁰⁻³⁴ Multiple studies showed that pTx is able to reduce hazards from implant-related heating at $B_0 \leq 3T$.^{12-14,19-24,35-38}

Because of this clinical potential, a thorough investigation of all pTx safety aspects at $B_0 \leq 3T$ is needed. RF safety in MRI is ensured by the IEC 60601-2-33 standard's³⁹ specific absorption rate (SAR) limits. PTx coils are treated like local transmit coils and thus have to adhere to strict local SAR limits, diminishing their performance, while single-channel driven body coils are not bound to local SAR limits and routinely violate them.^{40,41}

In principle, it is possible to measure SAR in-vivo indirectly by electric properties tomography (EPT)⁴²⁻⁴⁵ but necessary assumptions and limitations at tissue interfaces^{44,46} make the results uncertain and model dependent. Local SAR assessments are commonly done in silico, therefore, by simulations on human voxel models.³⁷ This approach relies on the availability of an exact digital model of the subject in the scanner.^{37,47,48}

A more common approach is the use of multiple pre-existing human voxel models,⁴⁹ but this requires the introduction of appropriate safety factors to accommodate for inter-subject variability.⁵⁰⁻⁵⁵ Multiple sources of uncertainty exist in this process. In particular, uncertainties regarding the exact digital patient model,^{50,53-56} tissue parameters and geometries,^{57,58} position⁵⁹⁻⁶¹ and state (e.g., breathing⁶²) need to be accounted for. It must

be emphasized that almost identical uncertainties would occur for single-channel body coils if they had to obey local SAR limits, too.

Local SAR assessments are then performed with Q-matrices^{2,63,64} compressed to virtual observation points⁴⁹ to reduce the number of required matrices by a factor $\sim 10^5$ in exchange for a few percent SAR overestimation.⁶⁵ For any complex RF shim vector (voltage amplitudes and phases applied to the different coil elements), the resulting peak spatial SAR can be calculated, and IEC compliance is ensured by rejecting all shim vectors generating excessive local SAR. This widely used safety approach will hereafter be referred to as 'SAR-controlled mode' (SCM). As it relies on exact phase information of each channel, SCM requires rather complex SAR-monitoring hardware.⁶⁶

In this work, two alternative phase-agnostic RF safety control modes are compared to the established SCM in terms of their B_1^+ performance when the patient's unknown anatomy and position in the scanner is mitigated with a safety factor.^{67,68} These are (i) a 'phase-agnostic SAR-controlled mode' (PASC) where the phase information in SAR assessment is neglected⁶⁸ and (ii) the 'power-controlled mode' (PCM), where only the maximum amplitude of all channels is supervised.⁶⁹ Next, the B_1^+ performance of pTx and the CP mode are compared, i.e., the safely achievable amplitudes and homogeneity after all modeling uncertainties are properly accounted for.

An idealized body coil with fixed geometry, but configurable with 1, 2, 4, 8, or 16 independent channels at field strengths $B_0 = 0.5T, 1.5T,$ and $3T$, is used to investigate the effect of not exactly knowing the patient's digital body model or precise position. Multiple simulations are employed to determine the safe excitation limits, i.e., the conditions where the permissible SAR limits are reached. These are termed 'anchor simulations', they reflect the system manufacturer's safety assessment. The excitation limits are tested in subsequent 'target simulations' on previously unseen body models or positions. This step mimics the unknown patient in the scanner, it allows to assess the uncertainty and, hence, the necessary safety factor, of the previous anchor analysis. The analysis is performed for all three control modes and the best achievable image quality, assessed in terms of mean B_1^+ and B_1^+ -homogeneity, is used to quantify the efficiency of either mode.

2 | METHODS

2.1 | Simulation setup

A birdcage-like cylindrical body-coil with two end-rings and 16 legs (356 mm coil radius, 352 mm leg length, 32 mm

FIGURE 1 (A) Simulation setup with human voxel model ‘Duke’ in the coil. (B) The unwound schematic of the birdcage coil of panel (A) with 48 ports marked by circles. Five different port combinations were investigated, with the number of independent RF channels varying from 1 to 16. See Figure S16 for a representation with voltage phasors. (C) Front view of all tested human voxel models with coil location (black dot in coil center), effective volume of coil (here shown for 3T, dotted cyan rectangle), head (dark blue), and torso (purple).

leg width, 50 mm end-ring thickness, material: perfect electric conductor [PEC]) surrounded by a concentric shield (1500 mm length, 376 mm radius, material: PEC) was used in all simulations. In total, the structure had 48 ports: one in the middle of each leg and one between each two legs on the end-rings, see Figure 1A. The coil was driven in five idealized configurations with channel counts $N_c = 1, 2, 4, 8,$ or $16,$ by combining ports accordingly, see Figure 1B. $N_c = 1$ is the CP mode and serves as a reference, $N_c = 2$ (two linearly polarized modes, independently fed at the 0° and 90° ports) is also available on many modern 3T scanners.

A realistic configuration, as investigated in Supporting Information A⁷⁰ for 3T and 16 channels, is required for any real-life implementation on a specific coil, but it might result different geometries for each channel count

and field strength with less generality. From a risk management perspective, it is advantageous to monitor the current in the coil directly, for example with pickup coils,⁶⁶ as uncertainties from components in the previous signal path are avoided. We therefore focused this work on the idealized configurations, that assume the knowledge of the current at each coil port.

Eleven human voxel models (10 from the virtual population⁷¹ plus the original XCAT model⁷²) were positioned for a cardiac exam (heart center at scanner coordinate $z = 0,$ backs resting on the $y = -170$ mm plane), see Figure 1C. The arms of the posable model Jeduk were spread by 3° to avoid a pathologic body loop.⁷³⁻⁷⁵ Such loop in model Glenn at 0.5T was masked, see Figures S19 and S20. While models XCAT and Eddie are based on the same male model of the visible human project,⁷⁶ the XCAT model is adjusted

to conform to the 50% percentile of US adults.⁷² Different positions of one model (Duke) in the scanner were also investigated, the results are presented in Supporting Information B.

Finite-difference time-domain (FDTD) simulations, each with one active and 47 non-active ports (treated as $Z_0 = 50 \Omega$ resistors), were carried out on an Nvidia Quadro GV100 graphics card in Sim4Life 6.2 (ZMT ZurichMedTech AG, Zürich, Switzerland) (model Eddy: Sim4Life 7.0) at frequencies of 21.3 MHz (0.5T), 63.9 MHz (1.5T), or 127.7 MHz (3T), all with 2 mm isotropic voxel size and frequency-specific tissue properties from the IT'IS database 4.0.⁷⁷ For virtual observation point (VOP) compression and auxiliary calculations an Intel Xeon Silver 4108 CPU was used. Total computation time for one configuration at 3T was ~ 12 h.

2.2 | Coil configurations

Only static, dimensionless RF shim vectors⁷ $\mathbf{u}_{N_c} = (u^{(1)}, u^{(2)}, \dots, u^{(N_c)})^T$ were analyzed in this work where $U^{(c)} = 1 \text{ V} \cdot u^{(c)}$ is the complex voltage amplitude of channel c and N_c is the channel count. For a given \mathbf{u}_{N_c} , the electromagnetic fields \mathbf{F} ($\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{E}$ or \mathbf{H}) at position $\mathbf{r} = (x, y, z)$ are calculated as superposition of N_c channel fields $\mathbf{F}_{N_c}^{(c)}$ which are themselves superpositions of the 48 port fields $\mathbf{F}_{48}^{(d)}$ by

$$\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{c=1}^{N_c} u^{(c)} \mathbf{F}_{N_c}^{(c)}(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{c=1}^{N_c} u^{(c)} \sum_{d=1}^{48} u_{N_c}^{(c,d)} \mathbf{F}_{48}^{(d)}(\mathbf{r}).$$

The five port-to-channel-conversion-matrices \mathbf{u}_{N_c} with sizes $N_c \times 48$ were derived with a simplified electromagnetic co-simulation,⁷⁸ see Supporting Information C.

2.3 | Normalized SAR VOPs

SAR VOPs⁴⁹ \mathbf{Q}_l ($l = 1 \dots N_l, N_l \approx 100$) were derived for all configuration combinations of the human voxel model, the position, the field strength and the channel count as described in Ref.³⁸ The VOPs were normalized to dimensionless matrices $\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_l$ by dividing each \mathbf{Q}_l by its respective IEC normal mode limit,³⁹ see Supporting Information D^{79–81} for details.

2.4 | Safety limits

Shim vectors \mathbf{u} are considered safe in terms of the IEC normal mode, if the following conditions are fulfilled for all the $N_l \hat{\mathbf{Q}}_l$ -matrices of a configuration.

In *SAR-controlled mode* (SCM), the requirement is ‘the dimensionless normalized peak spatial SAR $\widehat{\text{psSAR}}$ is limited to 1’; formalized as

$$\widehat{\text{psSAR}} \equiv \max_l \mathbf{u}^\dagger \hat{\mathbf{Q}}_l \mathbf{u} \leq 1. \quad (1)$$

In *phase agnostic SAR-controlled mode* (PASC), the requirement is ‘ $\widehat{\text{psSAR}}$ of the worst-case phase combination is limited by 1’; formalized as

$$\max_l |\mathbf{u}|^\dagger \left| \hat{\mathbf{Q}}_l \right| |\mathbf{u}| \leq 1, \quad (2)$$

where $|\cdot|$ denotes the element-wise absolute value as $|\mathbf{u}|^{(i)} = |u^{(i)}|$ and $|\hat{\mathbf{Q}}|^{(i,j)} = |\hat{Q}^{(i,j)}|$.

In *power-controlled mode*⁶⁹ (PCM), the requirement is ‘the maximum single channel amplitude of each shim vector is limited by α ’; formalized as

$$\max_c |u^{(c)}| \leq \alpha \equiv \min_l \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sum_{i,j=1}^{N_c} |\hat{Q}_l^{(i,j)}|}}, \quad (3)$$

see Supporting Information E for details. Implementation and hardware supervision on a real scanner are easier for PASC and PCM, since no phase information is needed. They are inherently less efficient, however, since the given limit must cover the worst case of all possible phase combinations.

2.5 | Anchor-target analysis

Safety limits based on simulation always need a safety factor since neither the actual subject’s anatomy nor its position are precisely known during the assessment. In the present work, this factor is determined by dividing the total number of N considered cases into n ‘training’ (termed: anchor) and $N - n$ ‘test’ datasets (termed: target). Random shim vectors \mathbf{u}_r are selected and scaled to fully exploit the IEC head and local SAR limits in the anchor simulations, or the partial-body and whole-body SAR limits in the target simulation if this limit is stricter, see Figure 2. The SAR-type distinction reflects that (only) partial-body and whole-body SAR are normally known even for unknown subjects. All counts $n \in \{1, \dots, N - 1\}$ and combinations of anchors were evaluated. For each control mode, coil configuration and B_0 , the safety factors are determined by the highest normalized local SAR ($\widehat{\text{psSAR}}$) encountered in any target simulation.

In the general case of multiple configurations being used for anchoring, the maximum in Eqs. (1, 2) is evaluated over all $\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_l$ of all anchor simulations while in Eq. (3) the lowest single channel amplitude limit α of all anchor configurations is used.

FIGURE 2 Schematic flow chart of the anchor-target analysis to derive a safety factor. See text for further explanation. (A) Each possible target in a given set of N configurations is selected for further analysis. Selecting more than one target is equivalent to reducing the number of configurations in the overall set and subsequent multiple runs with the same anchors and different targets. (B) The non-target configurations are used as anchor. (C) The selected target configuration. (D) The following analysis is carried out for each RF-shim vector in a set of M random RF-shim vectors. (E) The RF-shim vector is scaled such that the local and head SAR limit of the anchors as well as the global whole-body and partial-body SAR limits of the target are fulfilled. (F) The maximum of normalized local SAR and normalized head SAR is evaluated for the scaled ‘anchor-safe’ RF-shim vector. (G) This process is repeated for all N possible targets and M random RF-shim vectors. The overall maximum normalized SAR is used as safety factor. hd, head; wb, whole body; pb, partial body; hd, head; wb, whole body; pb, partial body.

In subsequent target simulations, which are always performed for a single configuration, the $\widehat{\text{psSAR}}$ of these scaled shim vectors $\mathbf{u}_{M,r}$ is calculated with the target’s $\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_i$:

$$\widehat{\text{psSAR}}(\mathbf{u}_{M,r}) = \max_l \mathbf{u}_{M,r}^\dagger \hat{\mathbf{Q}}_i \mathbf{u}_{M,r}.$$

This process is repeated for 10^6 random shim vectors $\mathbf{u}_{M,r}$ with $r = 1 \cdots 10^6$ (50% with random phases but equal amplitudes, 50% with random phases and amplitudes) and if the target’s maximum $\widehat{\text{psSAR}}$ exceeds unity it is used as safety factor s_M :

$$s_M = \max \{s'_M, 1\}, \quad s'_M = \max_{\mathbf{u}_{M,r}} \widehat{\text{psSAR}}(\mathbf{u}_{M,r}).$$

For PCM (only), a theoretical upper bound for $\widehat{\text{psSAR}}$ exists, as $\widehat{\text{psSAR}}_{\text{PCM,max}} \geq s'_{\text{PCM}}$ can be calculated directly from the amplitude limits α_a and α_t , of anchor and target simulations, respectively:

$$\widehat{\text{psSAR}}_{\text{PCM,max}} = \left(\frac{\min_a \alpha_a}{\alpha_t} \right)^2.$$

An example anchor-target analysis is demonstrated in Figure 3 for anchors Yoon-sun and Glenn and target Louis.

A global safety limit covering each conceivable patient configuration is not meaningful. A larger-bodied patient having a cardiac exam and a neonate having a brain exam require and deserve different limits to achieve both RF safety and performance. Appropriately selected patient groups are needed, therefore, and only the seven human models between 50 kg and 80 kg (Louis, Yoon-sun, Ella, Glenn, Jeduk, Duke, and XCAT, i.e., five males and two females) were used for this anchor-target analysis. Each possible combination of one to six anchors was evaluated on each of the remaining targets. For completeness, an analysis including all models despite their hugely different body masses, has also been performed. Predictably, this resulted in much higher safety factors > 6 , see Figures S21 and S22.

It should be reasonable to expect that the generated safety limit covers additional, completely unknown patients within the given patient group. This must be ensured with an appropriate safety factor that covers the model variability. The choice of the safety factor is essential to ensure safety and high RF performance. A too high safety factor is conservative, but limits performance more than necessary while a too low safety factor can result in damage for the patient. This work is therefore aiming at the lowest safety factor that still ensures safety for all

FIGURE 3 Schematic anchor-target analysis for the example of anchor models Yoon-sun and Glenn and target model Louis at 3T, eight channels with SAR-controlled mode. (A) Scaling of one example shim vector such that the local and head SAR limit of the anchors as well as the global whole-body and partial body SAR limits of the target are fulfilled. Anchors: Maximum intensity projections of normalized local SAR for one shim vector. The discrete steps between torso and extremities are caused by the different IEC limits. (B) Applying the same ‘anchor-safe’ shim vector to the target results in significant local SAR overshoots. (C) Distribution of \widehat{psSAR} in the target for 10^6 shim vectors; please note the logit x-axis. The example shim vector marked by ‘x’ is at the 1% percentile of the shim vectors with the highest \widehat{psSAR} . hd, head; wb, whole body; pb, partial body.

investigated models, if the most susceptible model would be unknown. The updated control-modes thus combine the safety factor of the leave-one-out anchor-target analysis with the VOPs of all configurations to ensure conservativeness. In the analyzed example, this corresponds to combining the safety factor of the anchor-target analysis with six anchors and one target with the VOPs of all seven models.

Once the safety factors are known, the safety limits are updated by multiplication of the cumulated \widehat{Q}_l of all configurations with s_M :

$$\widehat{Q}'_l = s_M \widehat{Q}_l, \quad l' \in \{1, 2, \dots, N_{l_1} + N_{l_2} + \dots + N_{l_N}\}.$$

In power-controlled mode, this is equal to dividing the lowest single channel amplitude limit α by $(s_{PCM})^{\frac{1}{2}}$:

$$\alpha' = \frac{1}{\sqrt{s_{PCM}}} \min_{\text{configurations}} \alpha.$$

Please note that PCM was treated like the SAR controlled modes in all mode comparisons, i.e., not the PCM-exclusive theoretical maximum but the highest actually encountered \widehat{psSAR} value was used.

To assess the B_1^+ performance for each control mode, the trade-off between best possible mean(B_1^+) and coefficient of variation $CV(B_1^+)$, both evaluated in the central imaging plane of the torso, was examined. To this

FIGURE 4 Maximum permissible relative total power $P(N_c, m) \propto \alpha(N_c, m)^2 N_c$ as a function of human voxel model mass m (A-C) or height h (D-F), normalized to the mean value of each channel count N_c and model for the given field strength. Each boxplot represents one model and contains the values of all five channel counts. The values are not comparable across different field strengths.

end, shim vectors were optimized with the Nelder–Mead algorithm,⁸² see Supporting Information F.

3 | RESULTS

3.1 | SAR limiting factors

The SAR analysis based on normalized Q-matrices³⁸ allows to investigate local and non-local SAR limits simultaneously. The limiting factor for the selected group of seven models in the 50–80 kg weight group is local 10 g-averaged SAR; never head, partial or whole-body SAR. Only if vastly different body models are compared, whole-body SAR can become limiting, see Figure S23. A median local SAR violation of factor 2.7 is observed for the CP mode hitting the whole-body SAR limit, see Figure S24.

3.2 | Model dependence (group 1)

3.2.1 | Power limits (only applicable to the power-controlled mode)

In PCM, the maximum permissible total power $P(N_c, \mu) \propto (\alpha(N_c, \mu))^2 N_c$ can be calculated directly. This was done for

all 165 combinations of five channel counts N_c , 11 human models μ with total body mass $m(\mu)$ and height $h(\mu)$, and three field strengths, see Figure S25.

Figure 4 illustrates $P(N_c, \mu)$ as a function of body-mass and body-height, for each B_0 , normalized to the mean across all channel counts and body models, i.e., each box shows the range across channel counts.

For $B_0 = 0.5\text{T}$ and 1.5T , the normalized total permissible power decreases with increasing body mass or height. In contrast, no clear trend can be observed for $B_0 = 3\text{T}$.

3.2.2 | Safety factors

For the anchor-target analysis with six anchor models and one target model, the $\widehat{\text{psSAR}}$ distribution, whose maximum defines the necessary safety factor, is shown in Figure 5. A hierarchy of models exists for $N_c = 1$ where all control modes are identical by design. Only the one model with the highest ‘SAR susceptibility’ can reach $\widehat{\text{psSAR}} > 1$ as it is included in the anchor group for all other models. For $N_c \geq 2$, PCM and PASCMS always show lower $\widehat{\text{psSAR}}$ than SCM and this difference increases with channel count. For up to four channels, the PCM distributions extend to $\geq 99\%$ of the theoretical $\widehat{\text{psSAR}}$ maximum (red stars) but for 16 channels the maximum is missed by

FIGURE 5 Violin plots of $\widehat{\text{psSAR}}$ for all field strengths, channel counts and target models in an anchor-target analysis with six anchor models and one target model (leave one out), where each violin represents 10^6 initial random shim vectors. Values > 1 mean that an anchor-safe excitation that also fulfills the target's partial and whole-body SAR limit exceeds the local SAR limit in the target model; the maximum value of each distribution defines the required safety factor. For the single-channel CP mode (circles) the three SAR modes become identical. Star symbols indicate the theoretical maximum (PCM only). For SCM, each tested shim vector must by construction produce $\widehat{\text{psSAR}} \geq 1$ in one target model.

$\sim 10 - 40\%$. This indicates that 10^6 random shim vectors are not sufficient to fully explore such high-dimensional parameter space, see Figure S26.

To investigate this aspect further, the optimization algorithm was used to find maximum $\widehat{\text{psSAR}}$ excitations for PCM and SCM for target Yoon-sun and the remaining 6 models as anchor, see Figure 6 and Supporting

Information G. These 'optimized' vectors reach the PCM upper limit with error below 0.5% for all channel counts. The realized $\widehat{\text{psSAR}}$ of 10^6 random shim vectors falls below the optimized $\widehat{\text{psSAR}}$ for $N_c \geq 16$ (PCM) and $N_c \geq 8$ (SCM) with increasing differences for higher channel count. Since phases are irrelevant, the PCM vector space is effectively lower dimensional than its

FIGURE 6 Maximum psSAR as a function of channel count for 3T of an anchor-target analysis with model Yoon-sun as target and all six other models (Louis, Ella, Glenn, Jeduk, Duke, XCAT) as anchors.

SCM counterpart and requires less test vectors to be explored.

The maximum psSAR of all random shim vectors for all combinations of anchor models and target model is shown in Figure 7 as a function of anchor count.

The maximum psSAR decreases with rising anchor-model count by construction. While safety factors of up to 6 are needed if only a single anchor model is used (16 channels, 0.5T; factor 5 for 8 and 16 channels at 3T) for SCM, the usage of six anchor models reduces that factor to ~2 for all SCM cases, see Table 1. For PCM and PASCAM, the observed maximum psSAR, i.e., the safety factors, are consistently lower compared to SCM, varying between ~3.6 (PCM) and ~4.8 (PASCAM) for one anchor (both four channels, 0.5T), and ~1.3 (PCM) and ~1.6 (PASCAM) for six anchor models (except for PCM at two channels and 3T).

3.2.3 | mean (B₁⁺) performance

The potential and the limitations of pTx for image quality are illustrated in Figure 8A–C for the example of the Duke model and eight channels. In the trade-off curves between mean(B₁⁺) and the CV as a B₁⁺-inhomogeneity surrogate, pTx excels if the subject model was exactly known and no safety factor is needed: the sweet spot of the pTx curve (here defined as shim vector with lowest cost $C = -\text{mean}(B_1^+/\mu T) + \lambda \times \text{CV}(B_1^+)$ for $\lambda = 3$; gray curve and symbols) offers 25% more mean(B₁⁺) and still improves CV (B₁⁺) by factors of up to 3, compared to the CP excitation. However, safety factors are normally needed and reduce the available power, and hence mean

(B₁⁺), for any given mode (colored curves). This affects pTx stronger than the CP mode: threefold homogeneity improvements are still possible but cost B₁⁺, particularly for PCM, where even at equal homogeneity the mean(B₁⁺) is reduced by 5–10%. SCM provides consistently 5%–20% more mean(B₁⁺) than PCM for the same homogeneity. PASCAM performs close to PCM for 0.5T and 1.5T and approaches SCM at 3T.

In Figure 8D–F, the mean(B₁⁺) performance of pTx shims compared to CP is shown for all control modes at image inhomogeneity $\text{CV}(B_1^+) = 0.1$, a typical value for CP excitation at 1.5T. Note that at 3T it takes $N_c \geq 4$ to achieve this homogeneity at least in some and $N_c = 16$ to meet it for all voxel models.

Necessarily, SCM without safety factor, i.e., assuming that the exact patient model is known, is always performing best with a 20–30% gain in mean(B₁⁺) compared to CP, largely independent of the channel count. Normally, however, the patient model is not known, safety factors must be included, and the overall mean(B₁⁺) drops by factors of 1.5–2. Compared to the CP mode with safety factor, pTx again provides ~20% more mean(B₁⁺) for SCM but ~10% less for PCM. With one exception (four channels at 0.5T), these numbers vary little with channel count or field strength. Note that for either control mode, the inclusion of the safety factor and basing the SAR assessment on all models dramatically reduced the box sizes and, hence, the model dependence. As seen before, PASCAM performs similar to PCM at 0.5T and 1.5T and approaches SCM for high channel counts at 3T.

A third comparison is shown in Figure 8G–I, where the cost function $C = -\text{mean}(B_1^+/\mu T) + \lambda \times \text{CV}(B_1^+)$ is evaluated for $\lambda = 3$ and the difference of the lowest shim vector cost to the respective CP-mode cost is plotted for each configuration. SCM always outperforms the CP mode, in this metric, while PASCAM and PCM fall behind the CP mode at 0.5T and 1.5T and have a slight advantage at 3T.

4 | DISCUSSION

4.1 | Safety aspects

The employment of pTx to improve B₁⁺ homogeneity⁴ or reduce implant heating³⁷ requires a solid framework to ensure patient safety even if no precise digital patient model is available. A method to assess RF safety for a given body coil but for an inherently unknown patient is presented in this work. Safety factors are derived from the highest psSAR in target models, yielding shim vectors that can safely be applied to unknown subjects, as long as these are not too different with respect to body mass. This procedure is applied for three different RF control modes

FIGURE 7 Maximum $\widehat{\text{psSAR}}$ as a function of anchor model count, channel count and B_0 field strength. Values > 1 mean that an anchor-safe excitation exceeds permissible local SAR limits in the target model. See Figure S27 for more details.

TABLE 1 Resulting safety factors for the anchor-target analysis with six anchors, cf. Figure 7.

Channel count	0.5T			1.5T			3T		
	SCM	PASC	PCM	SCM	PASC	PCM	SCM	PASC	PCM
1	1.02	1.02	1.02	1.24	1.24	1.24	1.37	1.37	1.37
2	1.16	1.09	1.03	1.27	1.20	1.08	1.72	1.55	1.51
4	1.86	1.41	1.03	1.52	1.14	1.11	1.80	1.63	1.30
8	1.66	1.11	1.03	1.79	1.06	1.03	2.17	1.38	1.32
16	1.82	0.95	0.85	2.04	0.86	0.77	2.25	1.17	1.04

FIGURE 8 (A–C) Trade-off between $\text{mean}(B_1^+)$ and B_1^+ inhomogeneity measured by $\text{CV}(B_1^+)$ (‘L-curves’) for target model Duke with 8 channels. The VOPs of all seven models and the safety factors of Table 1 were used for SCM, PASC and PCM (colored case). For comparison, the hypothetical case of an exactly known model (gray curve and symbols), SCM without safety factor and only the targets VOPs were used. The $\text{mean}(B_1^+)$ for a realistic target $\text{CV}(B_1^+) = 0.1$ is marked by a square, the shim vector with lowest cost $C = -\text{mean}(B_1^+/\mu T) + \lambda \times \text{CV}(B_1^+)$ with $\lambda = 3$ is marked with a triangle. (D–F) Relative $\text{mean}(B_1^+)$ at $\text{CV}(B_1^+) = 0.1$ of all safety limits and reference ‘model known’ as a function of B_0 field strength and channel count. All data are normalized to the CP mode value at the respective field strength. Higher values are better. At 3T, the desired target homogeneity is only achievable with higher channel counts. (G–H): Relative cost difference $\Delta C = k(C_l - C_{CP})$ of the lowest cost of all limits C_l relative to the CP mode C_{CP} with scalar constant $k(B_0)$ depending on B_0 . The curves are therefore not comparable across different B_0 . Cost function $C = -\text{mean}(B_1^+/\mu T) + \lambda \times \text{CV}(B_1^+)$ with $\lambda = 3$. Lower values are better.

SCM, PASC, and PCM, to investigate their mutual performance and robustness differences. In the Supporting Information B³³ it is further demonstrated how the same approach can be applied to uncertainties of the subject’s position.

A central result of the present work is the model dependence condensed in Figure 4–7. For $B_0 \leq 1.5T$, the permissible power to meet local SAR limits tends to decrease with either patient mass or height (Figure 4) while the commonly applied whole-body SAR limits generously allow even more power to be applied for heavier patients. Also, we find for all coil configurations, field strengths, voxel

models, or positions, that local SAR limits are inevitably vastly exceeded (by factors of ~ 2.5 , see Figure S24) if the whole-body SAR limit is fully exploited. This result indicates a need for a revision of IEC 60601–2–33.³⁹

Even in the limited weight range of 50–80 kg, we observe a pronounced model dependence of maximum $\widehat{\text{psSAR}}$ values but no single ‘most critical’ model: the highest SAR for a shim vector which is safe for all other models is found in the XCAT model at 0.5T, Jeduk at 1.5T, and Yoon-sun at 3T, see Figure 5. In consequence, any attempt to derive safety limits from simulating just one or two voxel models must fail, as clearly shown in Figure 7, unless

safety factors up to $s \approx 6$ are applied. For high channel counts $N_c \geq 8$, SCM requires $s > 2$ even for the best case of six known anchor and only one unknown target model. This is the result of (i) the many degrees of freedom pTx offers, in conjunction with (ii) the requirement that the worst case of all tested shim vectors, rather than, e.g., the most probable one, defines the safety factor. A safety factor of 6 can be observed for all 11 human voxel models when using 10 anchor models, see Figure S21. This indicates the need to preselect a suitable model group for a safety assessment: extrapolations across large mass differences are unsafe, while a too wide model group produces prohibitively over-conservative safety factors.

Figure 5 displays the difficulty to fully explore the excitation space with random vectors for $N_c \geq 8$. PCM offers the elegant solution of the theoretical SAR maximum, while for (PA)SCM the proposed active search for high-SAR vectors may be the best option for higher channel counts. Alternatively, one might question the worst-case paradigm: do we really need to safeguard for excitations with a $< 10^{-6}$ probability to occur?

It must be noted that the pTx degrees of freedom are only one part of the problem, the other one is the variability of local SAR itself: the seemingly unsuspecting case of a single-channel CP coil at 1.5T requires safety factor 1.3, even for six anchor models.

4.2 | Performance aspects

4.2.1 | Comparison of SCM, PASC, and PCM

By construction, all three control modes permit only excitations that are safe for all considered voxel models for all modes once the correct safety factor is applied. Differences exist, however, in terms of performance and robustness. SCM is the control mode of choice if $\text{mean}(B_1^+)$ is crucial. Sacrificing the phase information, as PCM and PASC do, costs performance, initially, but provides higher robustness and therefore lower safety factors with respect to unknown patient models or positional uncertainties, see Figures 5–7, S10–S15. The phase agnostic supervision modes are also easier to implement technically, e.g., by integrating calibrated root-mean-square detectors directly into the coil.⁶⁶

PASC approaches SCM in performance for higher channel counts that are advantageous for pTx applications like implant heating mitigation,^{22,36} see Supporting Information H. PCM's unique property to provide an easily calculable upper SAR limit for any given voxel model, without VOPs or iterating shim vectors, makes it the most robust control mode. This advantage must be evaluated against

the accompanying performance loss and the outcome of that comparison will likely be situation dependent.

4.2.2 | B_0 and channel-count dependence

No clear statement can be made about the field dependence of the SAR results (Figures 4–8). The variability of $\widehat{\text{psSAR}}$ across voxel models and channel counts or its dependence on the number of anchor models is similar for all B_0 , and no clear trend is observed. No field strength had a particular advantage or disadvantage in terms of safety parameters. Also, with respect to $\text{mean}(B_1^+)$ the relative performance gain of pTx vs. CP excitation varies surprisingly little with B_0 . The best pTx inhomogeneity is always a factor of $\sim 2 - 3$ smaller than for CP and for specific, homogeneity-demanding applications like quantitative MRI, pTx may be worthwhile even at 1.5T or below. If the CP homogeneity at 1.5T of $\text{CV}(B_1^+) = 0.1$ is regarded sufficient, however, static pTx provides no significant benefit in $\text{mean}(B_1^+)$ (Figure 8), once the safety factor is considered. On an absolute scale, the present results confirm the common knowledge that B_1^+ inhomogeneity increases with field strength; the need to do better than CP becomes most pressing at 3T.^{16,18}

Concerning the channel count N_c , the variability of $\widehat{\text{psSAR}}$ tends to increase with N_c (the violins in Figure 5 get larger), similarly as the number of anchor models needed to get the SCM safety factor down (Figure 7). Both dependences reflect the increasing dimensionality of the excitation vector space. Noteworthy is that this trend is absent or even weakly reversed, in the phase agnostic modes, since by design only the shim-vector phase-combinations that result in the highest SAR are considered.

4.3 | Limitations

UHF MR was not considered in this work since our focus was on the –normally vendor-built– body coil and very few such coils exist, so far for $B_0 \geq 7 \text{ T}$.^{3,84–90} The key elements of the described approach can also be applied at UHF, of course, where pTx is indispensable to cope with B_1^+ inhomogeneities.^{7–9}

Only static RF shimming is considered in this work, since it can be immediately applied to all existing pulse sequences and is thus the natural first step for pTx in the clinical market. More advanced techniques such as spokes^{91,92} and kT-points⁹³ are known to provide superior image quality and are ultimately needed to harvest pTx' full performance potential.

In this study, the same IEC SAR limits are applied to all coil configurations, even though the local 10 g-averaged

SAR limits are not formally required for the single-channel CP coil.³⁹ This is a purely regulatory difference, however, while here we are aiming at a physics-based comparison of different coil configurations.

Only the cardiac imaging position was simulated for the model uncertainty analysis in this study. We assume pTx to be less relevant for head scanning at $B_0 \leq 3T$ and expect the results for abdominal scanning to be qualitatively similar to the investigated cardiac case. The aim of this work was to investigate the feasibility and limits of the safety factor concept. For an actual safety assessment by a manufacturer, more human models and positions have to be examined. Also, a more detailed coil model, including the tuning/matching network would be needed. On the other hand, only a single field strength and channel configuration would need to be considered unless a manufacturer aims at a flexibly reconfigurable coil.

SAR assessments based on a *measured* patient model^{50,94} need no additional safety margins for model uncertainties and thus deliver, in principle, the highest mean B_1^+ . This approach requires extra time and additional effort, however. An important step towards patient-specific local SAR assessment are deep learning methods, that can rapidly generate body models from MR images,^{95–97} or directly generate local SAR maps from B_1^+ maps⁹⁸ or even directly from MR images^{99,100} and thus eliminate the time problematic. A large amount of sufficiently detailed¹⁰¹ digital human models for training is required on the flip side. The measured tissue distributions, however, also contain uncertainties, and scans at different positions may need to be acquired and combined, because the model is typically larger than the coil's field of view.

With our own computational resources, we estimate 500 days of computing time and 50 TB of raw data for a safety assessment of a given 3T body-coil. This is not negligible but should be manageable for an MR system manufacturer.

5 | CONCLUSIONS

The use of a pTx body coil at $B_0 \leq 3T$ is not limited by general safety concerns. Uncertainties in patient anatomy and position must be accounted for, however; either by simulating a large number of models and geometries or by imposing high safety factors. This allows for ~ 3 times lower inhomogeneity even at 0.5T, compared to CP excitation, but largely eliminates the potential advantage of pTx in terms of mean(B_1^+). An alternative second safety supervision mode, the 'power-controlled mode' PCM, sacrifices some performance but appears to be more reliable and robust in its SAR limits and can easily be implemented and

supervised in real-time. A third mode, the 'phase-agnostic SAR controlled mode' PASC, ranges in between SCM and PCM in terms of both simplicity and performance.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work has received funding from the EMPIR programme, co-financed by the Participating States and from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant number 17IND01 MIMAS and from the European Partnership of Metrology, co-financed by the Participating States and from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant number 21NRM05 STASIS. We thank ZMT for providing us the virtual family human body models within the MIMAS project. Open Access funding enabled and organized by Projekt DEAL.

ORCID

Johannes Petzold <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9503-0998>

Sebastian Schmitter <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4410-6790>

Berk Silemek <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8227-3632>

Lukas Winter <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4381-275X>

Oliver Speck <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6019-5597>

Bernd Ittermann <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4087-471X>

Frank Seifert <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7065-2528>

REFERENCES

1. Katscher U, Börner P, Leussler C, van den Brink JS. Transmit SENSE. *Magn Reson Med*. 2003;49:144-150. doi:10.1002/mrm.10353
2. Zhu Y. Parallel excitation with an array of transmit coils. *Magn Reson Med*. 2004;51:775-784. doi:10.1002/mrm.20011
3. Vaughan J t, Adriany G, Snyder C j, et al. Efficient high-frequency body coil for high-field MRI. *Magn Reson Med*. 2004;52:851-859. doi:10.1002/mrm.20177
4. Katscher U, Börner P. Parallel RF transmission in MRI. *NMR Biomed*. 2006;19:393-400. doi:10.1002/nbm.1049
5. Collins CM, Liu W, Swift BJ, Smith MB. Combination of optimized transmit arrays and some receive array reconstruction methods can yield homogeneous images at very high frequencies. *Magn Reson Med*. 2005;54:1327-1332. doi:10.1002/mrm.20729
6. Metzger GJ, Snyder C, Akgun C, Vaughan T, Ugurbil K, Van de Moortele PF. Local B1+ shimming for prostate imaging with transceiver arrays at 7T based on subject-dependent transmit phase measurements. *Magn Reson Med*. 2008;59:396-409. doi:10.1002/mrm.21476
7. Padormo F, Beqiri A, Hajnal JV, Malik SJ. Parallel transmission for ultrahigh-field imaging. *NMR Biomed*. 2016;29:1145-1161. doi:10.1002/nbm.3313
8. Deniz CM. Parallel transmission for ultrahigh field MRI. *Top Magn Reson Imaging*. 2019;28:159-171. doi:10.1097/RMR.000000000000204

9. Fagan AJ, Bitz AK, Björkman-Burtscher IM, et al. 7T MR safety. *J Magn Reson Imaging*. 2021;53:333-346. doi:10.1002/jmri.27319
10. Willinek WA, Gieseke J, Kukuk GM, et al. Dual-source parallel radiofrequency excitation body MR imaging compared with standard MR imaging at 3.0 T: initial clinical experience. *Radiology*. 2010;256:966-975. doi:10.1148/radiol.10092127
11. Eryaman Y, Akin B, Atalar E. Reduction of implant RF heating through modification of transmit coil electric field. *Magn Reson Med*. 2011;65:1305-1313. doi:10.1002/mrm.22724
12. Eryaman Y, Turk EA, Oto C, Algin O, Atalar E. Reduction of the radiofrequency heating of metallic devices using a dual-drive birdcage coil. *Magn Reson Med*. 2013;69:845-852. doi:10.1002/mrm.24316
13. Córcoles J, Zastrow E, Kuster N. Convex optimization of MRI exposure for mitigation of RF-heating from active medical implants. *Phys Med Biol*. 2015;60:7293-7308. doi:10.1088/0031-9155/60/18/7293
14. Eryaman Y, Kobayashi N, Moen S, et al. A simple geometric analysis method for measuring and mitigating RF induced currents on deep brain stimulation leads by multichannel transmission/reception. *Neuroimage*. 2019;184:658-668. doi:10.1016/j.neuroimage.2018.09.072
15. Silemek B, Acikel V, Oto C, et al. A temperature sensor implant for active implantable medical devices for in vivo subacute heating tests under MRI. *Magn Reson Med*. 2018;79:2824-2832. doi:10.1002/mrm.26914
16. Graves MJ. 3T: the good, the bad and the ugly. *Br J Radiol*. 2022;95:20210708. doi:10.1259/bjr.20210708
17. Setsompop K, Wald LL, Alagappan V, et al. Parallel RF transmission with eight channels at 3 tesla. *Magn Reson Med*. 2006;56:1163-1171. doi:10.1002/mrm.21042
18. Childs AS, Malik SJ, O'Regan DP, Hajnal JV. Impact of number of channels on RF shimming at 3T. *MAGMA*. 2013;26:401-410. doi:10.1007/s10334-012-0360-5
19. Gudino N, Sonmez M, Yao Z, et al. Parallel transmit excitation at 1.5 T based on the minimization of a driving function for device heating. *Med Phys*. 2015;42:359-371. doi:10.1118/1.4903894
20. Etezadi-Amoli M, Stang P, Kerr A, Pauly J, Scott G. Controlling radiofrequency-induced currents in guidewires using parallel transmit: controlling RF current using parallel transmit. *Magn Reson Med*. 2015;74:1790-1802. doi:10.1002/mrm.25543
21. McElcheran CE, Yang B, Anderson KJT, Golestanirad L, Graham SJ. Parallel radiofrequency transmission at 3 tesla to improve safety in bilateral implanted wires in a heterogeneous model: pTx at 3T to improve safety in bilateral implanted wires. *Magn Reson Med*. 2017;78:2406-2415. doi:10.1002/mrm.26622
22. McElcheran CE, Golestanirad L, Iacono MI, et al. Numerical simulations of realistic Lead trajectories and an experimental verification support the efficacy of parallel radiofrequency transmission to reduce heating of deep brain stimulation implants during MRI. *Sci Rep*. 2019;9:2124. doi:10.1038/s41598-018-38099-w
23. Godinez F, Tomi-Tricot R, Quesson B, et al. An 8 channel parallel transmit system with current sensor feedback for MRI-guided interventional applications. *Phys Med Biol*. 2021;66:21NT05. doi:10.1088/1361-6560/ac2fbc
24. Silemek B, Seifert F, Petzold J, et al. Rapid safety assessment and mitigation of radiofrequency induced implant heating using small root mean square sensors and the sensor matrix Q_s . *Magn Reson Med*. 2022;87:509-527. doi:10.1002/mrm.28968
25. Weinberger O, Winter L, Dieringer MA, et al. Local Multi-Channel RF surface coil versus body RF coil transmission for cardiac magnetic resonance at 3 tesla: which configuration is winning the game? *PLoS One*. 2016;11:e0161863. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0161863
26. Zhang Y, Liu Y, Sun B, Zhang X, Jiang X. Practical design of multi-channel MOSFET RF transmission system for 7 T animal MR imaging. *Concepts Magn Reson Part B Magn Reson Eng*. 2015;45:191-200. doi:10.1002/cmr.b.21313
27. Zhang B, Wang K, Jiang T. RF power design optimization in MRI system. *Magn Reson Lett*. 2021;1:89-98. doi:10.1016/j.mrl.2021.100006
28. Wu X, Zhang X, Tian J, et al. Comparison of RF body coils for MRI at 3 T: a simulation study using parallel transmission on various anatomical targets. *NMR Biomed*. 2015;28:1332-1344. doi:10.1002/nbm.3378
29. Guérin B, Gebhardt M, Serano P, et al. Comparison of simulated parallel transmit body arrays at 3 T using excitation uniformity, global SAR, local SAR, and power efficiency metrics. *Magn Reson Med*. 2015;73:1137-1150. doi:10.1002/mrm.25243
30. Brignole M, Auricchio A, Baron-Esquivias G, et al. 2013 ESC guidelines on cardiac pacing and cardiac resynchronization therapy: the Task Force on cardiac pacing and resynchronization therapy of the European Society of Cardiology (ESC). Developed in collaboration with the European Heart Rhythm Association (EHRA). *Eur Heart J*. 2013;34:2281-2329. doi:10.1093/eurheartj/ehs150
31. van der Graaf AWM, Bhagirath P, Götte MJW. MRI and cardiac implantable electronic devices; current status and required safety conditions. *Neth Heart J*. 2014;22:269-276. doi:10.1007/s12471-014-0544-x
32. Nordbeck P, Ertl G, Ritter O. Magnetic resonance imaging safety in pacemaker and implantable cardioverter defibrillator patients: how far have we come? *Eur Heart J*. 2015;36:1505-1511. doi:10.1093/eurheartj/ehv086
33. Soto DM. Current guidelines for MRI safety in patients with cardiovascular implantable electronic devices. *Nursing2022*. 2020;50:24-29. doi:10.1097/01.NURSE.0000651612.85237.fc
34. Bucciarelli-Ducci C, Vardas P. Reconsidering safety and reducing barriers to MRI in patients with cardiac implantable electronic devices. *Eur Heart J*. 2022;43:2479-2481. doi:10.1093/eurheartj/ehab469
35. Eryaman Y, Guerin B, Akgun C, et al. Parallel transmit pulse design for patients with deep brain stimulation implants. *Magn Reson Med*. 2015;73:1896-1903. doi:10.1002/mrm.25324
36. Guerin B, Angelone LM, Dougherty D, Wald LL. Parallel transmission to reduce absorbed power around deep brain stimulation devices in MRI: impact of number and arrangement of transmit channels. *Magn Reson Med*. 2020;83:299-311. doi:10.1002/mrm.27905
37. Winter L, Seifert F, Zilberti L, Murbach M, Ittermann B. MRI-related heating of implants and devices: a review. *J Magn Reson Imaging*. 2020;53:jmri.27194. doi:10.1002/jmri.27194
38. Petzold J, Schmitter S, Silemek B, et al. Towards an integrated radiofrequency safety concept for implant carriers in MRI based on sensor-equipped implants and parallel transmission. *NMR Biomed*. 2023;36:e4900. doi:10.1002/nbm.4900

39. International Electrotechnical Commission. *IEC 60601–2–33: Medical Electrical Equipment – Part 2–33: Particular Requirements for the Basic Safety and Essential Performance of Magnetic Resonance Equipment for Medical Diagnosis*. International Electrotechnical Commission; 2022.
40. Murbach M, Neufeld E, Kainz W, Pruessmann KP, Kuster N. Whole-body and local RF absorption in human models as a function of anatomy and position within 1.5T MR body coil. *Magn Reson Med*. 2014;71:839–845. doi:10.1002/mrm.24690
41. Murbach M, Neufeld E, Cabot E, et al. Virtual population-based assessment of the impact of 3 tesla radiofrequency shimming and thermoregulation on safety and $B_1 +$ uniformity: safety and thermoregulation in 3T RF shimming. *Magn Reson Med*. 2016;76:986–997. doi:10.1002/mrm.25986
42. Haacke EM, Petropoulos LS, Nilges EW, Wu DH. Extraction of conductivity and permittivity using magnetic resonance imaging. *Phys Med Biol*. 1991;36:723–734. doi:10.1088/0031-9155/36/6/002
43. Wen H. Noninvasive quantitative mapping of conductivity and dielectric distributions using RF wave propagation effects in high-field MRI In: Yaffe MJ, Antonuk LE, eds. *Medical Imaging 2003: Physics of Medical Imaging*; SPIE; 2003;5030:471. doi:10.1117/12.480000
44. Katscher U, Voigt T, Findeklee C, Vernickel P, Nehrke K, Dössel O. Determination of electric conductivity and local SAR via B_1 mapping. *IEEE Trans Med Imaging*. 2009;28:1365–1374. doi:10.1109/TMI.2009.2015757
45. Katscher U, Kim DH, Seo JK. Recent Progress and future challenges in MR electric properties tomography. *Comput Math Methods Med*. 2013;2013:e546562. doi:10.1155/2013/546562
46. Katscher U, Findeklee C, Voigt T. B_1 -based specific energy absorption rate determination for nonquadrature radiofrequency excitation. *Magn Reson Med*. 2012;68:1911–1918. doi:10.1002/mrm.24215
47. Córcoles J, Zastrow E, Kuster N. On the estimation of the worst-case implant-induced RF-heating in multi-channel MRI. *Phys Med Biol*. 2017;62:4711–4727. doi:10.1088/1361-6560/aa641b
48. Fiedler TM, Ladd ME, Bitz AK. SAR simulations & safety. *NeuroImage*. 2018;168:33–58. doi:10.1016/j.neuroimage.2017.03.035
49. Eichfelder G, Gebhardt M. Local specific absorption rate control for parallel transmission by virtual observation points. *Magn Reson Med*. 2011;66:1468–1476. doi:10.1002/mrm.22927
50. Meliàdo EF, van den Berg CAT, Luijten PR, Raaijmakers AJE. Intersubject specific absorption rate variability analysis through construction of 23 realistic body models for prostate imaging at 7T. *Magn Reson Med*. 2019;81:2106–2119. doi:10.1002/mrm.27518
51. de Greef M, Ipek O, Raaijmakers AJE, Crezee J, van den Berg CAT. Specific absorption rate intersubject variability in 7T parallel transmit MRI of the head. *Magn Reson Med*. 2013;69:1476–1485. doi:10.1002/mrm.24378
52. Shao Y, Zeng P, Wang S. Statistical simulation of SAR variability with geometric and tissue property changes by using the unscented transform. *Magn Reson Med*. 2015;73:2357–2362. doi:10.1002/mrm.25367
53. Le Garrec M, Gras V, Hang MF, Ferrand G, Luong M, Boulant N. Probabilistic analysis of the specific absorption rate intersubject variability safety factor in parallel transmission MRI. *Magn Reson Med*. 2017;78:1217–1223. doi:10.1002/mrm.26468
54. Steensma BR, Meliàdo EF, Luijten P, Klomp DWJ, van den Berg CAT, Raaijmakers AJE. SAR and temperature distributions in a database of realistic human models for 7 T cardiac imaging. *NMR Biomed*. 2021;34:e4525. doi:10.1002/nbm.4525
55. Malik SJ, Hand JW, Carmichael DW, Hajnal JV. Evaluation of specific absorption rate and heating in children exposed to a 7T MRI head coil. *Magn Reson Med*. 2022;88:1434–1449. doi:10.1002/mrm.29283
56. Malik SJ, Hand JW, Satnarine R, Price AN, Hajnal JV. Specific absorption rate and temperature in neonate models resulting from exposure to a 7T head coil. *Magn Reson Med*. 2021;86:1299–1313. doi:10.1002/mrm.28784
57. Alon L, Deniz CM, Carluccio G, Brown R, Sodickson DK, Collins CM. Effects of anatomical differences on electromagnetic fields, SAR, and temperature change. *Concepts Magn Reson Part B Magn Reson Eng*. 2016;46:8–18. doi:10.1002/cmr.b.21317
58. Kainz W, Neufeld E, Bolch WE, et al. Advances in computational human phantoms and their applications in biomedical engineering—a topical review. *IEEE Trans Radiat Plasma Med Sci*. 2019;3:1–23. doi:10.1109/TRPMS.2018.2883437
59. Wolf S, Diehl D, Gebhardt M, Mallow J, Speck O. SAR simulations for high-field MRI: how much detail, effort, and accuracy is needed? *Magn Reson Med*. 2013;69:1157–1168. doi:10.1002/mrm.24329
60. Kopanoglu E, Deniz CM, Erturk MA, Wise RG. Specific absorption rate implications of within-scan patient head motion for ultra-high field MRI. *Magn Reson Med*. 2020;84:2724–2738. doi:10.1002/mrm.28276
61. Kopanoglu E. Actual patient position versus safety models: specific absorption rate implications of initial head position for ultrahigh field magnetic resonance imaging. *NMR Biomed*. 2023;36:e4876. doi:10.1002/nbm.4876
62. Schoen N, Seifert F, Petzold J, et al. The impact of respiratory motion on electromagnetic fields and specific absorption rate in cardiac imaging at 7T. *Magn Reson Med*. 2022;88:2645–2661. doi:10.1002/mrm.29402
63. Bardati F, Borrani A, Gerardino A, Lovisolo GA. SAR optimization in a phased array radiofrequency hyperthermia system. *IEEE Trans Biomed Eng*. 1995;42:1201–1207. doi:10.1109/10.476127
64. Graesslin I, Homann H, Biederer S, et al. A specific absorption rate prediction concept for parallel transmission MR. *Magn Reson Med*. 2012;68:1664–1674. doi:10.1002/mrm.24138
65. Orzada S, Fiedler TM, Quick HH, Ladd ME. Local SAR compression algorithm with improved compression, speed, and flexibility. *Magn Reson Med*. 2021;86:561–568. doi:10.1002/mrm.28739
66. Graesslin I, Vernickel P, Börner P, et al. Comprehensive RF safety concept for parallel transmission MR. *Magn Reson Med*. 2015;74:589–598. doi:10.1002/mrm.25425
67. Petzold J, Ittermann B, Seifert F. Robustness of pTx safety concepts to varying subjects and subject positions. *Proceedings of the International Society for Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. Vol 29; ISMRM; 2021:2488.
68. Petzold J, Ittermann B, Seifert F. On the complexity of pTx systems in SAR assessment. *Proceedings of the International*

- Society for Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. Vol 30; ISMRM; 2022:2555.
69. Seifert F, Cassara A, Weidemann G, Ittermann B. Reliable and robust RF safety assessment of transmit array coils at ultra-high fields. *Proceedings of the International Society for Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. Vol 22; ISMRM; 2014:4891.
 70. Alagappan V, Nistler J, Adalsteinsson E, et al. Degenerate mode band-pass birdcage coil for accelerated parallel excitation. *Magn Reson Med*. 2007;57:1148-1158. doi:10.1002/mrm.21247
 71. Gosselin MC, Neufeld E, Moser H, et al. Development of a new generation of high-resolution anatomical models for medical device evaluation: the virtual population 3.0. *Phys Med Biol*. 2014;59:5287-5303. doi:10.1088/0031-9155/59/18/5287
 72. Segars WP, Sturgeon G, Mendonca S, Grimes J, Tsui BMW. 4D XCAT phantom for multimodality imaging research: 4D XCAT phantom for multimodality imaging research. *Med Phys*. 2010;37:4902-4915. doi:10.1118/1.3480985
 73. Mandel NS, Ramdial JL, Marcus EN. A second-degree burn after MRI. *CCJM*. 2017;84:348-349. doi:10.3949/ccjm.84a.15164
 74. Tagell L, Alcheikh A, Jurevics R, Nair AP. Thigh burn – a magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) related adverse event. *Radiol Case Rep*. 2020;15:2569-2571. doi:10.1016/j.radcr.2020.09.046
 75. Yang X, Zheng J, Wang Y, Long SA, Kainz W, Chen J. Body-loop related MRI radiofrequency-induced heating hazards: observations, characterizations, and recommendations. *Magn Reson Med*. 2022;87:337-348. doi:10.1002/mrm.28954
 76. Ackerman MJ. The visible human project: a resource for education. *Acad Med*. 1999;74:667-670.
 77. Hasgall P, Di Gennaro F, Neufeld E, et al. IT'IS database for thermal and electromagnetic parameters of biological tissues. *IT'IS Foundation* 2018. doi:10.13099/VIP21000-04-0
 78. Kozlov M, Turner R. Fast MRI coil analysis based on 3-D electromagnetic and RF circuit co-simulation. *J Magn Reson*. 2009;200:147-152. doi:10.1016/j.jmr.2009.06.005
 79. McIntosh RL, Anderson V. SAR versus VAR, and the size and shape that provide the most appropriate RF exposure metric in the range of 0.5-6 GHz. *Bioelectromagnetics*. 2011;32:312-321. doi:10.1002/bem.20642
 80. Lee J, Gebhardt M, Wald LL, Adalsteinsson E. Local SAR in parallel transmission pulse design. *Magn Reson Med*. 2012;67:1566-1578. doi:10.1002/mrm.23140
 81. Orzada S, Akash S, Fiedler TM, Kratzer FJ, Ladd ME. An investigation into the dependence of virtual observation point-based specific absorption rate calculation complexity on number of channels. *Magn Reson Med*. 2023;89:469-476. doi:10.1002/mrm.29434
 82. Nelder JA, Mead R. A simplex method for function minimization. *Comput J*. 1965;7:308-313. doi:10.1093/comjnl/7.4.308
 83. Nguyen BT, Pilitsis J, Golestanirad L. The effect of simulation strategies on prediction of power deposition in the tissue around electronic implants during magnetic resonance imaging. *Phys Med Biol*. 2020;65:185007. doi:10.1088/1361-6560/abac9f
 84. Vaughan JT, Snyder CJ, DelaBarre LJ, et al. Whole-body imaging at 7T: preliminary results. *Magn Reson Med*. 2009;61:244-248. doi:10.1002/mrm.21751
 85. Orzada S, Bitz AK, Johst S, et al. Analysis of an integrated 8-channel Tx/Rx body Array for use as a body coil in 7-tesla MRI. *Front Phys*. 2017. Accessed June 24, 2022;5. doi:10.3389/fphy.2017.00017
 86. Rietsch SHG, Orzada S, Bitz AK, Gratz M, Ladd ME, Quick HH. Parallel transmit capability of various RF transmit elements and arrays at 7T MRI. *Magn Reson Med*. 2018;79:1116-1126. doi:10.1002/mrm.26704
 87. Orzada S, Solbach K, Gratz M, et al. A 32-channel parallel transmit system add-on for 7T MRI. *PloS One*. 2019;14:e0222452. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0222452
 88. Fiedler TM, Orzada S, Flöser M, et al. Performance analysis of integrated RF microstrip transmit antenna arrays with high channel count for body imaging at 7 T. *NMR Biomed*. 2021;34:e4515. doi:10.1002/nbm.4515
 89. Fiedler TM, Orzada S, Flöser M, et al. Performance and safety assessment of an integrated transmit array for body imaging at 7 T under consideration of specific absorption rate, tissue temperature, and thermal dose. *NMR Biomed*. 2022;35:e4656. doi:10.1002/nbm.4656
 90. Gokyar S, Voss HU, Taracila V, et al. A pathway towards a two-dimensional, bore-mounted, volume body coil concept for ultra high-field magnetic resonance imaging. *NMR Biomed*. 2022;35:e4802. doi:10.1002/nbm.4802
 91. Saekho S, Yip C y, Noll DC, Boada FE, Stenger VA. Fast-kz three-dimensional tailored radiofrequency pulse for reduced B1 inhomogeneity. *Magn Reson Med*. 2006;55:719-724. doi:10.1002/mrm.20840
 92. Zelinski AC, Wald LL, Setsompop K, et al. Fast slice-selective radio-frequency excitation pulses for mitigating B inhomogeneity in the human brain at 7 tesla. *Magn Reson Med*. 2008;59:1355-1364. doi:10.1002/mrm.21585
 93. Cloos MA, Boulant N, Luong M, et al. kT-points: short three-dimensional tailored RF pulses for flip-angle homogenization over an extended volume. *Magn Reson Med*. 2012;67:72-80. doi:10.1002/mrm.22978
 94. Homann H, Börner P, Eggers H, Nehrke K, Dössel O, Graesslin I. Toward individualized SAR models and in vivo validation. *Magn Reson Med*. 2011;66:1767-1776. doi:10.1002/mrm.22948
 95. Huang Y, Dmochowski JP, Su Y, Datta A, Rorden C, Parra LC. Automated MRI segmentation for individualized modeling of current flow in the human head. *J Neural Eng*. 2013;10:066004. doi:10.1088/1741-2560/10/6/066004
 96. Nielsen JD, Madsen KH, Puonti O, et al. Automatic skull segmentation from MR images for realistic volume conductor models of the head: assessment of the state-of-the-art. *Neuroimage*. 2018;174:587-598. doi:10.1016/j.neuroimage.2018.03.001
 97. Brink WM, Yousefi S, Bhatnagar P, Remis RF, Staring M, Webb AG. Personalized local SAR prediction for parallel transmit neuroimaging at 7T from a single T¹-weighted dataset. *Magn Reson Med*. 2022;88:464-475. doi:10.1002/mrm.29215
 98. Meliàdò E f, Raaijmakers A j e, Sbrizzi A, et al. A deep learning method for image-based subject-specific local SAR assessment. *Magn Reson Med*. 2020;83:695-711. doi:10.1002/mrm.27948
 99. Gokyar S, Robb FJL, Kainz W, Chaudhari A, Winkler SA. MRSaiFE: an AI-based approach towards the real-time prediction of specific absorption rate. *IEEE Access*. 2021;9:140824-140834. doi:10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3118290
 100. Gokyar S, Zhao C, Ma SJ, Wang DJJ. Deep learning-based local SAR prediction using B1 maps and structural MRI of

the head for parallel transmission at 7 T. *Magn Reson Med.* 2023;90:2524-2538. doi:10.1002/mrm.29797

101. Carluccio G, Akgun C, Vaughan JT, Collins C. Temperature-based MRI safety simulations with a limited number of tissues. *Magn Reson Med.* 2021;86:543-550. doi:10.1002/mrm.28693

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information may be found in the online version of the article at the publisher's website.

Figure S1. Comparison of the absolute amplitudes between the ideal configuration and a realistic configuration.

Figure S2. Positions of the ports in the coil model with human model Duke.

Figure S3. Comparison of the CP mode B_1^+ distribution of realistic configuration and ideal configuration.

Figure S4. B_1^+ maps of all 16 channels of the realistic configuration.

Figure S5. B_1^+ maps of all 16 channels of the ideal configuration.

Figure S6. Comparison of the 1-norm Q matrix values of realistic configuration and ideal configuration for model Duke.

Figure S7. Comparison of the 1-norm Q matrix values of realistic configuration and ideal configuration for model Ella.

Figure S8. Anchor-target analysis with Ella and Duke for the ideal configuration and the realistic configuration.

Figure S9. Coil center positions of simulations with human voxel model 'Duke' to investigate position uncertainty.

Figure S10. Anchor-target analysis for small z-shifts.

Figure S11. Safety factors needed for 1D positional bilateral inference or unilateral inference.

Figure S12. Boxplots of the maximum $\widehat{\text{psSAR}}$ of all anchor-target runs of model Duke for a given z-shift for the SAR-controlled mode.

Figure S13. Boxplots of the maximum $\widehat{\text{psSAR}}$ of all anchor-target runs of model Duke for a given z-shift for the phase agnostic SAR-controlled mode.

Figure S14. Boxplots of the maximum $\widehat{\text{psSAR}}$ of all anchor-target runs of model Duke for a given z-shift for the power-controlled mode.

Figure S15. 3D inference from the 8 corners of a rectangular cuboid to the central point for 3 T and 8 channels.

Figure S16. The unwound schematic of the birdcage coil with the voltage phasors for each channel configuration.

Figure S17. Determination of the effective volume of the used RF coil.

Figure S18. Trade-off between mean (B_1^+) and $\text{CV}(B_1^+)$ for model Duke with a spinal cord dummy implant.

Figure S19. Maximum intensity projections of point SAR in models Jeduk and Glenn.

Figure S20. Maximum intensity projections of 10 g averaged SAR in models Jeduk and Glenn.

Figure S21. Violin plots of $\widehat{\text{psSAR}}$ for all field strengths, channel counts and target models in an anchor-target analysis with 10 anchor models and 1 target model (leave one out).

Figure S22. Maximum $\widehat{\text{psSAR}}$ as a function of anchor model count, channel count and B_0 field strength.

Figure S23. Maximum intensity projections of normalized local SAR for one shim vector for anchor model Dizzy and target model Fats.

Figure S24. Boxplots of the maximum normalized 10g-averaged local SAR, partial-body SAR and head SAR.

Figure S25. Maximum permissible total power $P(N_c, m) \propto \alpha(N_c, m)^2 N_c$ as function of channel count and human voxel model mass for $B_0 = 0.5$ T, 1.5 T, and 3 T.

Figure S26. Distribution of $\widehat{\text{psSAR}}$ for an anchor-target analysis with anchors Glenn and Yoon-sun and target Louis.

Figure S27. Maximum $\widehat{\text{psSAR}}$ as a function of anchor model count, channel count and B_0 field strength.

How to cite this article: Petzold J, Schmitter S, Silemek B, et al. Investigation of alternative RF power limit control methods for 0.5T, 1.5T, and 3T parallel transmission cardiac imaging: A simulation study. *Magn Reson Med.* 2024;91:1659-1675. doi: 10.1002/mrm.29932